

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECT OF FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS ON THE ADAPTATION OF CHILDREN TO THE KINDERGARTEN ENVIRONMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7736509>

Abstract: This article describes the role and importance of parents during the socio-psychological adaptation of a child to preschool education. In addition, it is discussed what other family members should take into account during the period of adaptation of the child to this new environment. A number of tips and systematic recommendations on how to carry out the stages of adaptation in order to facilitate the child's adaptation have been given.

Key words: socio-psychological adaptation, maladaptation, skill, competence, educational organization, game activity, cognitive knowledge, communication, preparation.

The organization of preschool education, which is the initial link of continuous education for the full upbringing of a child, his development and preparation for adulthood, is of particular importance in the education of a perfect person. Thus, the process of adapting the child from the family circle to the kindergarten environment, to new conditions, makes a radical change in the child's life. Adaptation is different for each child. Because every child has its own behavior and characteristics. In addition, adaptation to a new environment is also related to how many people there are in the child's familiar family environment and how the relationship with them is formed. So, in the kindergarten, the child learns to communicate with peers and adults in a wide range, independence and organizational skills are formed. Develops skills for various practical activities (game, learning, cognitive).

It is advisable for parents not to take their children directly to the kindergarten environment, but on the contrary, family members should get used to the child for a while. So what should be considered in this? Acquaintance of the child with relatives, neighbors, apart from the family members, creates an opportunity to communicate with them, and gets used to communicating with strangers. Going through the above process plays a positive role in the child's transition from the home family environment to a completely different world full of people and things that are unfamiliar to the child.

In some children, the adaptation process is carried out by easily coping with changes. But for most children, this process shows fear, tears, and various whims. What does the process of adjusting to kindergarten involve?

The process of adapting to certain conditions is called adaptation. Everyone has to enter a new community environment at different ages. In this place, adaptation to a new environment is simply not possible not only for children, but also for adults. Because easy or difficult adaptation depends on the attitude of the members of this community towards the newcomer.

If the child cries when entering the kindergarten, it will definitely affect the mood of the parents. Day by day, having a dream child will cause a decrease in work productivity for the day. In order to avoid the above inconveniences, parents and educators are considered the

most important participants in the period of adaptation and adaptation. So, how the family prepares the child for the kindergarten environment:

- get used to a strict daily routine;
- active communication with parents and relatives;
- stay in the environment of peers for a long time;
- listening to the instructions of a stranger (under parental supervision);
- leaving the usual comfort (comfortable for oneself) zone and entering new communities;

Also, it is difficult for the child to get used to a sharp decrease in the level of personal attention.

It is natural that fundamental changes in the life of a small person cause neurotic reactions. They are expressed by tears and hysteria, refusal to eat, whims, frequent illnesses, etc.

Adaptation steps:

- preparation;
- key;
- the final.

Parents should approach each of them with full responsibility.

Preparatory stage: First of all, it begins with the gradual expansion of the child's social circle. Keeping the positive emotions gained in games together with other children. Enhancing the child's joy by discussing interesting situations during the game with the child. In addition, tell the child about the kindergarten in advance and show it. His attention should be drawn to the fact that his future kindergarten will have bright and colorful rooms, beautiful playgrounds, and a group of peers who play interesting games.

What parents should do at the moment is to choose kindergartens that are convenient for them based on their needs. You can take an excursion there with your child by prior agreement with the kindergarten staff. A casual acquaintance with the future caregiver and children will not hurt either. Taking advantage of this situation, it would be more appropriate if the mother and the educator were introduced to the words with which they express their child's natural needs. In addition, the child has the opportunity to have positive impressions by showing what his peers do in kindergarten.

Before visiting the kindergarten, the child should be taught basic movements:

- go to the toilet;
- self-feeding;
- wash your hands,
- wash your face,
- brushing teeth, at least two months before, it is very important to adapt the child to the routine as much as possible. That is, waking up, eating breakfast, walking, etc. should be done at the same time. This is especially true for daytime sleep. Weekends should also be spent in the prescribed mode. It is necessary to try to make the child's mood positive from early morning. In the first days, it is desirable that the child does not stay in the kindergarten during the day. That is, the total time he stays in the kindergarten is from 1 to 3 hours. In some cases, a mother can stay with her child, participate in games, and help with training. The more positive emotions the child has at this stage, the faster he will get used to it and will not be dissatisfied with staying in a new team. In addition, it is recommended to leave the child in the nursery for daytime sleep.

The duration of the main stage of adaptation includes a different period for each child. In normal case, the fastest and easiest adaptation is enough for two weeks. And in children who are difficult to adapt, this process lasts up to six months.

After the adaptation process is complete:

- the child calmly starts going to kindergarten in a good mood;
- has a good relationship with the teacher and peers;
- actively plays in his group, participates in training;
- eats well, sleeps well.
- the emotional and physical condition of the child is completely normalized.

In order for parents to be patient and calmly accept the period of adaptation of the child to kindergarten, it should be noted that the adaptation occurs during the following periods:

- quick and easy adaptation - from 2 weeks to a month;
- medium adaptation - from 30 days to 2 months;
- severe adaptation - up to six months.

There are very few children who quickly and easily adapt to a new environment. For many children, this process is delayed. Children experiencing maladaptation are very capricious, cry a lot, refuse to perform usual actions, eat, require constant attention, etc. This can be repeated for a very long time. As a result, the child starts to get sick. Only the joint efforts of parents and educators will allow children and adults to get out of this difficult period faster.

What affects a child's adaptation to kindergarten? Factors affecting the process of a child's adaptation to a preschool educational institution include:

- his age;
- general physical development and health;
- the main thing is the presence or absence of the ability to understand and express one's own needs;
- compliance with the agenda at home and in the preschool education organization;
- level of communication and communication;
- development of game activity;
- playing independently with toys;
- implementation of elementary hygiene procedures;
- communicating with peers and strangers.

If the family does not have an agenda for preparing the child for the educational organization, then a state of inability to adapt (disadaptation) is observed. In addition, the child may have specific habits that negatively affect his development. If the child is very attached to the mother, it is much more difficult to adapt.

At what age is it better to send a child to kindergarten? Often this problem is solved depending on the existing conditions. If his mother has to go to work early, then the question disappears by itself. The period of maternity leave is usually up to 3 years. This period is very important for child care. It should be remembered that the child should be given time to adapt, that is, the adaptation process should begin one and a half to two months before the mother goes to work.

Now, if we approach the problem from a psychological point of view, then the optimal period of getting used to the children's team is considered to be from 3 years old. It is during this period that children develop a constant interest in peers, team games and communication

with them. In addition, children of this age, as a rule, have simple self-care skills, they can control the physiological needs of the body.

How can you help your child adjust to kindergarten? Many parents are very worried about leaving their child in preschool in the early days. This is considered normal, because the child remains in an unfamiliar circle, in an unusual environment. The emotional state of adults is very important for children. Therefore, you should try to keep calm in front of the child and help him overcome such a difficult period.

It is important to have conversations with the child about kindergarten. It is better to conduct these conversations with a little indifference, because talking to the child in a tone of pity and pity can increase maladjustment. Conversations should be not only introductory and narrative in nature, but also interesting and encouraging to join peers. The older the child, the more often he asks leading questions that lead to the expression of his opinion. Together with the parents' stories and the child's comments, it makes it possible to gradually get used to the organization. Do not forget that in kindergarten, the child should act more independently. The purpose of conversations between parents and the child before going to kindergarten is to convince the child that the new environment and the people in it will not harm the child, that it is the child's "second home" and a group of friends for fun team games. It is here that new knowledge and skills are learned.

Step-by-step adaptation for kindergarten:

- start active preparation 2-3 months ago;
- conversations with the child about kindergarten;
- employees establish close contact with children;
- patiently pay attention to the child, take care of it;
- do not make excessive demands about what you have learned from him in the first days:

Tell the teacher in advance about your child's habits (character, behavior, sleep patterns, appetite) and available skills. Try to control your emotions and fears. Never show these negative anxious feelings to the child. Never share your negative feelings with the child (thinking about him every day). With this, he can feel that he is in a very poor and bad situation. Therefore, a holistic approach, mutual trust and mutual support are very important. Parents should ask educators about how their child behaves, eats, sleeps, and take their advice into account.

Recommendations to facilitate the adaptation process in the child:

- do not delay the time of going to kindergarten;
- come up with a motivation for a quick goodbye;
- gradually increase the time the child spends in kindergarten;
- do not constantly buy things from the store so that he can go to kindergarten;
- do not make unreasonable breaks in visiting a children's institution (attendance);
- do not be too late to pick up from kindergarten (no more than 8 hours);
- think about the morning goodbye actions (kissing, hugging, shaking hands, etc.) and repeat them every day;
- always fulfill your promises to him (hold the standard);
- If it is really difficult for the baby to say goodbye to his mother, then it is better for another family member to take him to the kindergarten;
- Take control of any questions and situations;

How to reduce stress in a child? The biggest stress for a baby is to say goodbye to his mother. Parental separation with the right behaviors can reduce the stress level that occurs when preparing a child for kindergarten. That is, it is important to teach the child to stay with other family members, to be occupied with a toy while the mother is gone.

Let's look at the reasons for fear in a child:

- new environment;
- unfamiliar faces;
- communicating with strangers;
- the assumption that I will be forgotten and not taken home.

If the first three reasons for fear are quickly eliminated, and these reasons mainly depend on the work of the educator, the general readiness of the child for kindergarten, the fourth one depends on the behavior of parents. If you promised to come to him early one day, don't delay at all. It is also important to casually ask about how the day went, about his friends, about the lessons he had, what he had for lunch.

Here is a list of recommendations that every adult and parent should follow when taking a child to a preschool:

- "If you don't listen to me, if you don't behave, I will take you to kindergarten!" it is impossible to say. With your words, the kindergarten will be perceived as a place of punishment.
- If the child cries when saying goodbye, do not scold him or get angry. The best assistant here is patience, attention, kind words and actions (hugs, kisses, don't forget to tell him that you love him).
- Do not promise the impossible. For example, to bring a toy or candy. If the child asks you to get something, but you don't have enough money for it, explain it to him frankly. With this, qualities such as understanding your presence or absence are formed in the child.
- When picking up your child, try not to be left behind alone. Do not make this mistake especially in the first days of kindergarten.
- Praise him often, listen carefully and with interest to his stories about his life, achievements and failures in the team.
- Another of the mistakes of the parents during the adaptation of the child is that the child constantly observes the behavior of the parents, their mood, tone of voice, and facial expressions. Therefore, it is recommended that they keep themselves under constant control.
- When talking to the child, speak with respect and goodwill towards the educators, this will reveal the key to the positive attitude of the child to the new environment.
- Sometimes parents throw the child in the kindergarten as a distraction and try to escape quickly. This is completely wrong, the child soon notices that his mother is gone and begins to worry about the possibility that he will not return. It is a very effective way to say good-bye to the child and take him after finishing his work, and to make sure that he will participate well in the training. It is not possible to draw boundaries in conversations with the child because he does not understand the work of adults, in any case, explaining the situation to him correctly will ensure that the child will be thoughtful later on.

Therefore, the period of adaptation is a period of restructuring of the body, overcoming psychological difficulties. How easy or difficult it is for a child to overcome such obstacles largely depends on the parents. In order to avoid mistakes in raising a growing person,

mothers and fathers should pay more attention to expanding knowledge about the age-related characteristics of the child's mental and physical development.

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